

POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND THE RUSSIAN FEDERATION

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<https://www.doi.org/10.37547/ejlfas-v03-i02-p1-08>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th January 2023

Accepted: 07th February 2023

Online: 08th February 2023

KEY WORDS

Russia, Uzbekistan, Central Asia, foreign policy concept, foreign policy priorities.

ABSTRACT

The research topics are determined both by the general trend of activation of integration processes in the CIS, and by strengthening bilateral cooperation Russia and Uzbekistan. The interstate dialogue between the two countries has not always been formed in a positive friendly way. However, today, while maintaining many political and economic difficulties (migration policy, trade relations, etc.) There have been obvious moves towards not just normalization of relations, but with draw al take them to a new qualitative level. Taking into account the priority nature of the development of the post-Soviet space, both states express a firm position on overcoming the difficulties of the modern period, solving state tasks and, in general, strengthening the strategic Russian-Uzbek dialogue. At the same time, it is stated that it is necessary to expand the interstate dialogue at the expense of new areas, such as military-technical, trade-economic, humanitarian and cultural industries. Special attention is paid to the period after 2016 d, when there was a change of power in the Republic of Uzbekistan and there were certain changes in its foreign policy.

The Uzbek SSR was created on October 27 1924 It is worth noting that the republic was composed of various countries and regions, in including Samarkand region, Syrdarya region, Ferghana region, Khorezm region, Bukhara region and Karakalpak ASSR. In addition, the Tajik ASSR was included in the Uzbek. Before 1929, the SSR Republic was formed in accordance with the declaration of the First Founding Congress of Soviets of the Republic on February 13, 1925, which elected the Presidium. The CEC and approved the composition of the SNR Uzbek, after that, in 1925, the Uzbek SSR became part of the USSR as a union republic.

The Uzbek SSR is located in the central and northern parts of Central Asia. The population of the country was 19906 thousand people, which was in third place among the countries of the USSR. On the territory of the Uzbek SSR, it occupied 447.4 thousand km² and was the 5th in terms of territory among the USSR states. Uzbekistan played an important role

in the USSR during the years of social development. In fact, Uz Bekistan has become an industrial-agrarian republic. In addition, at the same time, light industry and a powerful cotton base of the USSR developed in this region.

The Uzbek SSR was one of the leading producers in the post-Soviet space in terms of cotton and other products. The Uzbek SSR was the leader in industry and production among the countries Central Asia. For example, the Uzbek SSR took the first place in cotton growing, since 85% of irrigated lands were engaged in this production and annually produced from 60 to 70% of the entire Soviet production. The following graph describes the development of the Uzbek cotton industry SSR from 1913 to 1991. As can be seen, the cotton industry has begun to develop after the Second World War. The cotton industry was as important for the country's economy as the USSR. However, there were fluctuations in the Uzbek cotton industry. For example: from 1980 to 1985, the cotton industry peaked and two years later the year decreased from 1986 to 1987, and then it peaked again in 1988, after which it gradually continued to decline.

During the war, Uzbekistan received more than a million people from the occupied regions of Russia - Ukraine and Belarus. Of these, 200,000 were children. The population of Uz Bekistan reacted understandingly to these people and provided the necessary humanitarian assistance. They were allocated 135 000 m² of housing. A lot has been done for employment of displaced persons. Only in Tashkent in 1941-1942 about 240 thousand people were employed. During the war, many soldiers were wounded, including soldiers of the Uzbek SSR. At the beginning of the war, the Government of the Republic began to create additional hospitals. October 1, 1941 in the People's Commissariat of Health of Uzbekistan 47 hospitals were built that could to accept 14950 patients equipped with necessary equipment. Evacuated hospitals were allocated the best buildings of Tashkent and other major cities Uzbek SSR. By the end of 1942, 113 vaccination hospitals with 39140 beds were located on the territory of Uzbekistan. During the war, 164,382 wounded were hospitalized, of which 87% received treatment. More than 750 enterprises, organizations and collective farms took care of the sick to ensure full-fledged nutrition at the front, and the entire Uzbek people took care of the wounded.

The victory of the USSR over the armed forces of Germany, the selfless work of the country's workers, including the Uzbeks, is crucial. The industry of Uz Bekistan was sent to the front during wars 2100 combat aircraft, 17342 transport aircraft, 17100 mortars, 4500 weapons of mass destruction, about 60,000 military equipment, 22 million units of mines and 500,000 tanks, 3 million radio tubes, 300,000 parachutes, 5 trains, 18 sanitary trains, 2,200 portable kitchens were delivered to 2861,5 thousand units of troops. It is worth noting that after the Second World War, the policy of industrialization of the Uzbek SSR began to develop. And it is also worth noting that after the end of this war, the Uzbek SSR mainly turned focus on the development of domestic production and exports.

Moscow played a significant role in the reconstruction of Tashkent after the earthquake. The Moscow government helped the people of Uzbekistan by building new apartments for them in a short time. The Uzbek SSR is on its way to independence. Gaining independence was not easy for Uzbekistan. According to the researcher, the foundation for the step towards independence was laid by Sharaf Rashidov, who was the first secretary of the Communist

Party of Uzbekistan from 1959 to 1982. During his stay in the government, he tried to gather his relatives and friends so that the Uzbek SSR could work together and be independent. At that time, Moscow chose mainly Russians for the government, but step by step in Uzbekistan, the number of Uzbeks in the government began to grow, thanks to politics Sh. Rashidov, who wanted to make Uzbekistan less controlled by Muscove. After the death of Sh. Rashidova Moscow again took control of the Uzbek SSR. By the end of the 1980s, some dissenting intellectuals created political organizations to express their grievances.

The most important of them, "Birlik" ("Unity"), initially advocated the diversification of agriculture, a program to save the dried-up Aral Sea and the proclamation of the Uzbek the official language of the republic. These questions were chosen in part because they caused real concern, and partly because they were safer ways of expressing broader discontent with the Uzbek government. In their public debates with Birlik, the government and the party have never lost their positions. As it became especially clear after the introduction Karimov as the head of the party, most Uzbeks, especially outside the cities, still supported the Communist Party and the government. The intellectual leaders of Birlik have never been able to reach out to a wide range of the population. The key moment that stimulated the movement towards independence was the Soviet coup attempt against Gorbachev in August 1991, most of the leaders of Central Asia actively or passively supported the coup. Uzbekistan becomes independent. By the spring of 1991, the Parliament of all five republics had declared its sovereignty. Uzbekistan has become similar to the four other Central Asian states that gained independence on December 26, 1991, when the USSR formally collapsed. Coup attempt against the Gorbachev government by dissatisfied hardliners in Moscow, which took place in August 1991, served as a catalyst for the independence movement throughout the Soviet Union. Despite the initial indecision of Uzbekistan to resist the revolution, the Supreme Soviet of Uzbekistan declared the republic independent on August 31, 1991.² In December 1991, a referendum on independence was held with 98.2% of the votes of voters. In the same month, the parliament was elected, and I. Karimov was elected the first president of the new country. Based on the study of the role and structure of the Uzbek SSR, the following conclusions can be drawn: if we talk about the economy, the Uzbek SSR was one of the leading among the republics of the post-Soviet space in cotton production and industrial production.

The contribution of the Uzbek people to the victory in the Great Patriotic War was also significant. Among the Uzbeks – 69 Heroes of the Soviet Union. UzSSR accepted many children and people from other republics. The people of the Uzbek SSR took care of them. That is why the Uzbek people are called the great Uzbek people. Principles and mechanisms of Uzbekistan's foreign policy. After gaining independence, Uzbekistan began to develop bilateral relations with foreign countries, mainly with neighboring ones. In addition, Uzbekistan has created the main tasks of its foreign policy and has begun to act in accordance with these tasks. The main objectives of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

They are further strengthening the independence and sovereignty of the State, increasing the role of the country and international politics, creating the most favorable conditions for ensuring national and regional security, stable and dynamic development of the national economy. Continuing the progressive movement towards an open democratic state, joining the ranks of the developed countries of the world.

The main foreign policy objectives of Uzbekistan at the present stage are:

1. Consistent development of international cooperation in political, trade, economic, cultural, humanitarian, scientific, technical and other fields;
2. Creation of the most favorable foreign policy conditions for the effective implementation of democratic reforms in the country and dynamic processes of modernization of society and economy;
3. Preserving and strengthening peace and stability in Central Asia, turning the region into a zone of security and sustainable development, promoting peace and stability in Afghanistan;
4. Formation of a balanced and multi-planned system of strategic partnership with the leading states of the world and international organizations, maintenance of geopolitical equilibrium in the region, broad diversification of trade, economic, technological, transport and other relations of Uzbekistan;
5. Use of political, diplomatic and international legal mechanisms, including preventive diplomacy measures, for timely resolution of existing or emerging problems in the region;
6. Strengthening the international image of Uz Bekistan as a reliable political and economic partner, increasing the investment, tourist, cultural and historical attractiveness of the country in the international arena;
7. Active development and use of mechanisms of bilateral and multilateral cooperation to stimulate the attraction of foreign direct investment and high technologies in priority sectors of the national economy;
8. Assistance in the formation and development of a multifaceted system of international transport and communication corridors, ensuring reliable and stable access of Uzbekistan to world markets;
9. Ensuring comprehensive protection of the rights and interests of citizens and legal entities of the Republic of Uzbekistan abroad.

Based on these tasks, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The priority region of Uzbekistan is Central Asia;

The foreign policy of the Republic is mainly focused on the development of trade, economy, cultural, scientific and technical cooperation;

- Uzbekistan supports peace and security;

- Uzbekistan makes special efforts to develop its international image as a reliable political and economic partner.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has established the fundamental principles of its foreign policy, which is emphasized by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan as follows: the fundamental principles of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are mainly the conduct of an open, pragmatic and balanced foreign policy based on national interests, as well as the development of equal and mutually beneficial relations with other countries on the basis of generally recognized international norms and principles, respect for sovereignty, territorial integrity and non-interference in Internal affairs, peaceful settlement disputes are not the use of force.

Uzbekistan conducts peaceful policy and does not participate in military-political blocs and reserves the right to leave any interstate entity in the event of its transformation into a military-political block. It is worth noting that Uzbekistan pursues a policy of independence and balance of power between the main players present in Central Asia (Russia, China, the United States and the European Union). Over the years, his participation in regional organizations has been controversial. Uzbekistan's foreign policy at the new stage has had an impact on neighboring countries, especially on the Central Asian region. Asia, in which the Republic of Uzbekistan is currently pursuing a foreign policy called "Central Asia first of all". A few months after the elections, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, approved five main priority directions for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and this is planned to be done by 2021.⁴ The Strategy of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes there are five large chapters, and each chapter consists of several parts that define this chapter. The political and legal framework of bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and Russia. First of all, it should be noted that Uzbekistan became an independent state on August 31, 1991. Accordingly, after gaining independence, Uzbekistan began to consider itself the main strategic force in the Central Asian region after the collapse of the Soviet Union. Considering its population and central location, as well as its political elite, RU perceived Russia as the main rival of their leading role in Central Asia.

The first step towards diplomatic relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation was taken in 1992, when the two sides signed an agreement concerning diplomatic relations between Uzbekistan and Russia. In the same year, Moscow and Tashkent signed five diplomatic protocols and agreements, four of which are still they are in effect, and one of them is currently not in effect. The first protocol on the establishment of diplomatic relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation, signed on March 20, 1992.⁶ In this diplomatic document, the context It mainly concerns the initial stage of the development of international relations between the two states, and is also aimed at promoting the implementation of the goals and principles of the CIS, and this diplomatic document is still in force. In accordance with the agreement and protocols signed in the same year, Uzbekistan and Russia agreed to develop their bilateral diplomatic relations at the level of cooperation. Currently, Russia has an embassy in Tashkent, and Uzbekistan has embassies in the Russian Federation, more precisely in Moscow, St. Petersburg and Novosibirsk. Due to two months after the signing of the agreement, another diplomatic document was signed concerning the agreement of the two states on the basis of international relations, as well as friendship and cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation. This two-party agreement is different from the previous one. The difference is that, it is much broader and concerns various aspects of bilateral relations between Russia and Uzbekistan. The agreement includes 27 articles based on territorial issues and respect of the two States for their history, language, nation and peaceful relations. In addition, it should be noted that article 10 is based on the economic relations of the Russian Federation and Uzbekistan, which the republic plays at the initial stage of the development of bilateral relations in the field of economics.

It should be noted that the meetings of the heads of Uzbekistan and Russia within the framework of international summits also played an important role in the development of bilateral relations. The meeting of the President of Uzbekistan and Russia took place in March

1994 in Moscow, and B. Yeltsin and I. Karimov signed another set of agreements concerning the extension of the previous agreement on military cooperation, which emphasized that the parties should not allow anyone to use their territory to attack another signatory. In accordance with this bilateral agreement both parties must provide each other friend military facilities and troops when needed.

The legal framework of Russian-Uzbek cooperation consists of more than 200 inter-state, intergovernmental and interdepartmental agreements concerning various areas, including military, economic and humanitarian cooperation. Comprehensive cooperation between The Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation are developing on the basis of Agreements on Strategic Partnership (2004) and Allied Relations (2005). The bilateral agreement on strategic partnership between the Russian Federation and the Republic of Uzbekistan was signed on June 6, 2004, which played a significant role in the development of bilateral relations between the two states. Strategic Partnership Agreement, It includes 15 articles dealing with various personal aspects. For example: Article 3 concerns each other's support when considering issues affecting their national interests in international procedures, and article 7 concerns interaction with military associations of two states, for example: delivery of military products to the Republic of Uzbekistan from the Russian Federation, training in military schools, bilateral military cooperation and others. The Treaty on Allied Relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation is considered to be the most important a bilateral agreement that plays the main role in the development of the international strategic partnership between Uzbekistan and Russia also plays an important role in the development of comprehensive cooperation between the two countries. The Agreement includes 16 articles related to various aspects. For example: Article 5 is devoted to joint work to strengthen peace, strengthening stability and security at the global and regional levels. In particular, the treaty emphasized the further strengthening of the central role the UN and its Security Council, implementation the goals and principles enshrined in the OSCE documents, prevention and resolution of conflicts and the solution of regional and global problems of security and stability. In addition, in the 6th article, the Russian Federation and the Republic of Uzbekistan has agreed to cooperate in the fight against terrorism and similar actions and illegal drug trafficking. The contract is currently in force, and its effective date is July 19, 2006. When we talk about the development of bilateral relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation, we must remember about official visits presidents of two states. After that, it is worth mentioning the official visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Moscow on April 14-15, 2013.¹ During his visit to Moscow, I. Karimov highlighted issues related to the terrorist organization "Taliban" and the fight against it. And he also said that we, as SCO member states, should work on the spot to find a solution to such problems, and he also said that without Russia these problems cannot be solved. In addition, they discussed the most important topics of bilateral cooperation, outlined concrete plans for the future in the political, trade, economic, cultural and humanitarian spheres, and also signed a program of economic cooperation between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Uzbekistan. Government of the Russian Federation for 2013-2017, It should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation have

similar positions on various issues of foreign and regional policy and are simultaneously working on the further development of their foreign policy interactions.

The Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation. The Federation carries out mutual support in international organizations, including the UN, the SCO and the CIS. In addition, Uzbekistan and Russia have similar foreign policies in various aspects. For example; they both support the policy of preserving and strengthening peace and stability in the CIS region, and at the same time support cooperation in the fight against international terrorism and extremism and drug trafficking.

Tashkent and Moscow want to strengthen cooperation within the framework of international organizations such as the UN, the SCO and the CIS. According to several sources. There is a great potential. The next visit of the President took place in Tashkent, where Dmitry Medvedev (the third President of the Russian Federation) visited Uzbekistan on a working visit in July 2011, He took part in discussions at the summit in Tashkent. The Presidents of Uzbekistan and Russia discussed the prerequisites for cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation in ensuring the stability of security in the Central Asian region. During his visit, several agreements were signed, including the agreement of the two states on the representation of diplomatic representations of Russia and Uzbekistan, as well as the program of cooperation of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. The next visit, which played an important role in bilateral relations between the two states in the trade, economic, humanitarian and cultural spheres, was an official visit the President of Uzbekistan to the Russian Federation in Ufa on July 10, 2015. During the visit of the President of Uzbekistan to Russia, several issues were discussed, including issues that lag behind in the development of two-party relations in such areas as trade, economy, culture and humanitarian issues, as well as issues of regional security. It is worth noting that culture plays an important role in bilateral relations, and two states, Russia and Uzbekistan, respect each other's cultural traditions and history. As a result, Uzbekistan respects Russian culture, 22 Russian cultural centers are operating in the republic, uniting regional and national public cultural associations, as well as more than 700 schools receive education in Russian. After independence, bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and Russia intensified, especially in such areas as culture, science, information technology, healthcare, sports and tourism. The intensification of bilateral relations in these areas can be seen in the agreement signed on March 19, 1993, which concerned cooperation in the fields of culture, science and technology, education, health, information, sports and tourism. The Agreement includes 12 articles that play a significant role in the development of bilateral relations between the two states and currently it works. The Republic of Uzbekistan and The Russian Federation has signed various agreements, treaties and protocols in the field of tourism on the way to developing bilateral relations in this area. According to the study, Russia and Uzbekistan signed an agreement on tourism in 1993, and 24 years later another agreement was signed in 2017 on the development of cooperation in the field of tourism, within the framework of which this agreement was signed under the second President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Sh.Mirziyoyev visited Moscow for the first time as the second President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017. This means that after 24 Uzbekistan has touched on this topic since the

Republic of Uzbekistan is making efforts to expand bilateral relations with the Russian Federation.

The next visit of Russian President Vladimir Putin to Uzbekistan took place on December 10, 2014, and this visit played an important role in the development of economic relations over the next five years. During his visit to Uzbekistan, several bilateral agreements were signed, including intergovernmental agreements, economic cooperation, and at the same time, the two sides discussed how to develop bilateral relations in the field of economic cooperation. The Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation the Federation is considered strategic partners, as they have a higher trade turnover compared to other states in the Central Asian region. Asia, with the exception of Kazakhstan. It is worth noting that on the basis of the strategic partnership, an agreement was signed on the development of economic cooperation on 5 years from 2015 to 2019, this bilateral economic agreement outlines the main directions of economic cooperation between Uzbekistan and Russia. The Agreement includes 6 articles, which specify the main goals and areas of activity. The articles mainly concern the cooperation of the two states in the field of transport and communications, as well as the inter-governmental commission on economic cooperation between the Russian Federation the Federation and the Republic of Uzbekistan. In addition, it should be noted that the heads of state of Uzbekistan and Russia regularly meet at multilateral summits and meetings within the CIS and SCO.

The next official visit of the President of Russia and Uzbek. Two years later, when Uzbek President Islam Karimov paid an official visit to Russia on October 25-26, 2016.¹ This official and working visit also played an important role in the development of bilateral relations between the two states. The parties discussed the prospects of development bilateral cooperation in various spheres, and also discussed interaction within the CIS and the SCO. There was also an exchange of views on current issues in the world, as well as in the CIS region. As part of this official visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to Russia some agreements were signed, cooperation program, memoranda in various fields. It is worth noting that Uzbekistan relies on military cooperation with Russia in border issues of the republic. According to the agreement between Russia and Uzbekistan in the field of military cooperation, Russia should provide military assistance Uzbekistan not only in case of direct aggression from the south, but also to strengthen the borders Uzbekistan. The southern border of Uzbekistan is important for the republic, as the first President of Uzbekistan said at a meeting with the President of Russia in 1992: "We care about the security of our southern border" and We expect military support from Russia. ³⁰ On May 1992, the Uzbek-Russian agreement was signed in Moscow. Most of the points of the agreement related to military issues, including the training of personnel for the Uzbek army in Russian military schools. Together with Russia, Uzbekistan managed to maintain a "buffer zone" in the Northern Afghanistan by protecting the authorities in the southern part of Uzbekistan. This "buffer zone" ensured the security of the southern the borders of Uzbekistan. After Aliban came to power in the north of Afghanistan, the "buffer zone" was practically destroyed. A critical situation has arisen on the border. At that time, Uzbekistan turned to Russia for military-technical assistance within the framework of the Agreement on Military-Technical Cooperation and the bilateral agreement between Uzbekistan and Russia.

According to the study, Russia and Uzbekistan are strategic partners and at the same time have allied relations since 2004. The main base of bilateral documents of Uzbekistan and Russia has a protocol on the establishment of diplomatic relations, an agreement on strategic partnership and an agreement on allied relations. These two third-party documents play a fundamental role in interstate relations between Russia and Uzbekistan. Based on the considered process and the areas of study of the first chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Cooperation between Russia and Uzbekistan is mutually beneficial. If you go back Historically, Uzbekistan was one of the main producers in the USSR. Based on the study, it can be noted that after the collapse of the USSR, there were no stable bilateral relations between Russia and Uzbekistan, the bilateral relations of which began to develop after the signing of the agreement on strategic partners in 2004 and the agreement on allied relations in 2005. Currently, Uzbekistan's foreign policy is changing, the republic is open for investment, and many foreign countries are currently they invest in Uzbekistan. Tashkent has a good influence on the Central Asian region, which is beneficial for both the republic, so it is for the countries of Central Asia.

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